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PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 23

Issue 10

Pages: 1292-1302

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2233

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13352216

Manuscript Accepted: 07-23-2024

Integrating the 5E Instructional Learning Cycle in Developing Slide-Based Instructional Material in Mathematics 9

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Abstract

This study aimed to develop and evaluate Slide-Based Instructional Material for Mathematics 9 at Maximo L. Gatlabayan Memorial National High School during the 2023-2024 academic year. The research specifically sought to address four key questions: identifying the quarter with the lowest mastery in Mathematics 9 based on the Learning Outcomes Assessment (LOA) of 2022-2023, evaluating the developed instructional material across content quality, instructional quality, technical quality, and accuracy by both Mathematics teachers and experts, examining any significant differences between the evaluations of these two groups, and gathering comments and suggestions for enhancing the material. A descriptive research method was employed, involving 10 Mathematics teachers and 10 experts from District II of the City Schools Division of Antipolo. Statistical analysis included the use of weighted mean to assess evaluations and independent sample t-tests to compare the evaluations of the two groups. The findings revealed that the second quarter had the lowest learning outcomes, which informed the development of the instructional material. Both groups rated the material as very satisfactory, with grand weighted means of 3.82 and 3.85. No significant differences were found between the evaluations of the two groups. Respondents praised the material for its comprehensive content, effectiveness in promoting active engagement, and quality. Suggestions for enhancement included incorporating video links, using varied templates, adjusting slide transparency, and adding real-life examples to improve understanding and retention.

Keywords: *Slide-Based Instructional Material, Mathematics*

Introduction

Education plays a vital role in forming and enhancing individuals' abilities and expertise. Education is not only about imparting knowledge and skills, but it also aims to develop critical thinking, problem-solving abilities, creativity, and resilience in individuals so that they can navigate challenges and contribute meaningfully to society. Moreover, it seeks to nourish emotional and interpersonal aptitudes and instill values relevant to leading healthy and fulfilling lives on both an individual and social level (Marujo & Casais, 2021).

It is of utmost importance for an educator to be fully committed to providing top-notch education to their students. Being a teacher requires diverse duties that require considerable dedication and unyielding commitment. Creating a positive and engaging learning environment involves cultivating a positive atmosphere, establishing transparent rules, delivering constructive criticism, and encouraging students to take ownership of their academic growth. Mayfield (2019) states that part of the responsibility of being an educator is to grasp students' individual needs and preferences and respond to them in a way that fosters an inclusive learning atmosphere conducive to progress and improvements. To effectively handle a group of learners with diverse backgrounds, an educator must possess the traits of adaptability, creativity, and patience to effectively overcome the problems associated with being an educator.

In this context, mathematics emerges as a critical area of the curriculum globally recognized for its foundational role in science, technology, and other vital sectors (Suleiman & Hamed, 2019). Mathematics serves as a powerful tool for unveiling the connections between elements, for understanding how things work, and for making predictions about what might happen in the future. Mathematics provides the fundamental basis for numerous essential aspects of modern daily life, including currency, building constructions, the internet, and even medical facilities. However, many students find math to be a tough subject. According to Langoban (2020), teachers confront a big problem in making mathematics more approachable to students. Higher-level mathematics is more complex than lower-level math, hence many students face greater challenges when they attend higher levels of education.

In the Philippines, the state of mathematics education has long been a cause for concern, as students consistently face significant challenges in this subject. Alarming, the 2022 PISA results indicated that the country's performance in mathematics remained nearly the same as the 2018 results, with students scoring below the average OECD level. Notably, low achievers in mathematics became stronger, while there was no significant change in performance among high achievers. Only 16% of Filipino learners obtained at least Level 2 proficiency in mathematics, far below the average OECD of 69% (NEDA, 2023).

Addressing these educational challenges, constructivism is one of the most dominant pedagogical frameworks that promotes active learning, critical thinking, and knowledge construction by students (Ugwuozor et al., 2020). According to Piaget and Vygotsky, constructivism proposes to engage learners with their environment to construct knowledge and comprehension. Moreover, Constructivism emphasizes socialization and cooperative learning as key to enhancing students' higher-order thinking skills, promoting a learner-centered approach that encourages responsibility for their learning.

Instructional models such as the 5E, 6E, and 7E, are based on the constructivist concept of learning. These methods prioritize a learner-centered approach that actively engages and promotes experiential learning. This approach aligns with methodologies that prioritize students' active engagement in their learning processes to develop knowledge and comprehension. Integrating a teaching and learning process, such as the 5E instructional model, is considered beneficial as it supports the mental processes of examining and combining new knowledge in a constructivist educational environment. Adu and Folson (2023) investigated how the 5E model was used in math classes. The application of the five-stage learning model, known as the 5E instructional learning cycle, often leads to remarkable improvements in students' levels of mathematical comprehension and performance. More importantly, studies revealed that learners who were taught in accordance with the 5E model had more active involvement and interaction during math activities than those using traditional pedagogical approaches.

The role of teachers in making lessons interactive and engaging became hard when the pandemic started, making it difficult for teachers to disseminate and teach the lessons and for students to understand the lessons being taught to them. As the pandemic forced traditional classrooms to transition to distance learning, educational technology became vital in maintaining academic performance and supporting the continuity of learning (Torres, 2022). This shift has underlined the essential nature of technology in education, transforming it from a luxury to a necessity, particularly in the implementation of English language programs (Pratiwi & Waluyo, 2022). The integration of educational technology not only facilitates the learning process but also enriches it by providing a wide range of resources that can improve the educational experience through interactive and multimedia-enhanced classes using internet platforms, virtual learning environments, and educational applications. Additionally, there has been a notable increase in financial investment in educational institutions aimed at integrating various technologies into educational systems, highlighting a commitment to adapting to innovative educational methods (Uspayanti et al., 2022).

Despite these technological advances, Maximo L. Gatlabayan Memorial National High School faces challenges in various subjects, particularly in Mathematics. This is evident in the learning outcomes assessment (LOA) of the School Year 2022-2023, which showed a decline from the first to the fourth quarter, with scores of 44.28, 37.92, 45.26, and 44.30, respectively, which is far from the division target which is 80.00 Mean Percentage Score (MPS). One potential factor contributing to this low MPS is the school's struggle to implement asynchronous learning effectively due to unreliable internet connections in both the school premises and nearby areas. Although the school has facilities and resources for instruction, the unstable internet connectivity presents a considerable obstacle to the smooth delivery of educational content.

In response, the researcher initiated a purposeful endeavor of integrating the 5E instructional learning Cycle in the development of slide-based instructional material in Mathematics 9. This indicates a proactive approach to leveraging digital tools for instruction and learning, emphasizing the significance of technology in education, especially in scenarios where a stable internet connection might be lacking. This strategy reflects the teacher's adaptability and commitment to maximizing the benefits of technology within the constraints of their teaching environment. By employing the 5E instructional learning cycle, a teaching method rooted in constructivist principles, each phase of the teaching model, engage, explore, explain, elaborate, and evaluate, offers a framework to teach dynamic learning based on the student. Through maintaining technology integration within each phase, this approach not only brings students into a way of engaging and active learning but also institutes structured explanations, opportunities for detailed understanding and conclusive assessment.

Therefore, this study aimed to integrate the 5E instructional learning in developing Slide-based instructional material in Mathematics 9. Such a study offers perceptions, suggestions, and points for improving Filipino learners' mathematical proficiency. This adheres to Department Memorandum No. 13, s. 2023, which aims to provide an enhanced system of numeracy and literacy among the students, supporting Section 5 of Presidential Decree No. 6-A, which stipulates, "One of the educational objectives is to design, utilize and improve instructional technology and materials".

This instructional material could greatly enhance mathematical literacy while acknowledging the need for innovation with the use of slide presentations. Furthermore, teachers could also use this to enhance learners' academic performance through active participation and experiential learning.

Research Questions

This study aimed to develop and evaluate slide-based instructional material in Mathematics 9 integrating the 5E instructional learning cycle at Maximo L. Gatlabayan Memorial National High School, City Schools Division of Antipolo for School Year 2023-2024. Specifically, this study aimed to determine the following questions:

1. What Quarter in Mathematics 9 exhibited the lowest mastery according to the results of the Learning Outcomes Assessment of School Year 2022-2023?
2. What is the evaluation provided by Mathematics teachers and expert respondents on the developed Slide-based instructional material in Mathematics 9 to the following criteria:
 - 1.1. content quality;
 - 1.2. instructional quality;
 - 1.3. technical quality; and

- 1.4. accuracy and up-to-datedness?
3. Is there a significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed slide-based instructional material in Mathematics 9?
4. What comments and suggestions were given by the respondents to enhance the created instructional material?

Methodology

Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive research design. Anisa et al. (2021) stated that this method collects and compiles data to describe a phenomenon or event. It involves obtaining information using observation, interviews and surveys to describe and understand the characteristics of such a subject in a comprehensive way. By examining and summarizing information, researchers are able to present a comprehensive yet condensed overview of what they are researching.

The researcher chose to conduct a descriptive study to evaluate the development of instructional material in Mathematics 9 based on content quality, instructional quality, technical quality, and accuracy and up-to-datedness.

Respondents

The research was conducted at the City Schools Division of Antipolo during the School Year 2023-2024. The respondents in this study were ten (10) teachers specializing in Mathematics and ten (10) experts, including Mathematics Master teachers, Mathematics Head teachers and ICT Coordinators. These individuals were carefully chosen using Purposive Sampling, a method that involves selecting individuals who are expected to provide the most relevant and significant information for the research objectives (Dick Sagoe et al., 2023).

The selected respondents evaluated the developed instructional material by providing their assessment of its content quality, instructional quality, technical quality, and accuracy and up-to-datedness.

Instruments

The tool employed for the data collection in this study was the Survey questionnaire.

The utilized questionnaire was adapted from the DepEd LRMS non-print evaluation rating sheet and the study of Buitre (2023) entitled "Electronic Strategic Intervention Material (E-SIM) in Grade 7 (Biology): Effects on Student's Performance" and further modified by the researcher. The evaluation of the teachers and expert respondents on the slide-based instructional material in Mathematics 9 used specific criteria including content quality, instructional quality, technical quality, and accuracy and up-to-datedness. Each statement in the criteria was rated on a scale of 1 to 4, with corresponding verbal interpretations: Not Satisfactory, Poor, Satisfactory, and Very Satisfactory.

Procedure

The first phase of this research involved the retrieval of the Learning Outcomes Assessment from the previous School Year. After identifying the quarter with the lowest Learning Outcomes, it was used as the basis for the development of slide-based instructional material in Mathematics 9. The researcher then created the slide-based instructional material and submitted it to the adviser for revisions, suggestions, and feedback to enhance areas requiring improvement.

The researcher sent a letter to the Antipolo City Schools Division Research Unit, Marikina Polytechnic College Research, and Development Office requesting approval to disseminate and validate the Survey Questionnaire. A letter with the same content was also given to the school principal of Maximo L. Gatlabayan Memorial National High School, where the survey questionnaires were distributed to the respondents. Before commencing the study, the researcher ensured that the letter's content complied with the criteria stipulated in R.A.10173 – Data Privacy Act of 2012, aiming to prevent future difficulties and uphold the privacy of individuals.

After receiving approval to conduct the study, respondents were selected. The researcher distributed the created instructional material in Mathematics 9 and survey questionnaires to the teacher and expert respondents. The slide-based instructional material and the data privacy consent were incorporated into the survey questionnaire form.

The data collected from the two groups of respondents were examined and organized for statistical analysis. The data were thoroughly evaluated, presented systematically, and analyzed. This research aimed to compare data acquired from two groups of respondents to determine whether there was a substantial gap in their evaluations. After the statistical analysis, the data were subsequently organized and tabulated to facilitate a systematic presentation and analysis.

Data Analysis

The study employed the following statistical tools to describe and analyze the collected data concisely.

Weighted Mean. This was employed to determine the respondent's evaluation on the developed slide-based instructional material using

the 5E Instructional Learning Cycle, focusing on its content quality, instructional quality, technical quality, and accuracy and up-to-datedness.

t-test for Independent Samples. This was employed to evaluate if there is a significant difference in the evaluation of the developed instructional material utilizing the 5E Instructional Cycle between the two groups of respondents, namely Mathematics teachers and experts.

Table 1. *Scale, Range and Verbal Interpretation*

<i>Range</i>	<i>Scale</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretations</i>
3.26 – 4.00	4	Very Satisfactory
2.51 – 3.25	3	Satisfactory
1.76 – 2.50	2	Poor
1.00 – 1.75	1	Not Satisfactory

Ethical Considerations

For this study, the researcher implemented the following ethical considerations;

Prior Consent. Participants signed consent forms to confirm their willingness to participate after being fully informed about the research's purpose and processes, and the respondents have the option to exclude names in the survey.

Data Privacy. All information collected from participants during the study were handled with the utmost confidentiality, emphasizing the commitment to protect individual privacy. Strict protocols were in place to ensure that all personal data remained secure and inaccessible to unauthorized parties. Upon the completion of the study, to further uphold ethical standards and ensure the safety of participant information, all collected data were permanently deleted, eliminating any potential for future access or misuse.

Anonymity and Confidentiality. Participants were provided with the choice to exclude their names from the survey questionnaire to maintain anonymity. This option aimed to empower participants to control the level of personal information they disclosed, enhancing their sense of privacy and confidentiality in the study.

Voluntary Participation. Teacher participants willingly engaged in this study, fully aware that their involvement was completely voluntary and without obligation. No coercion or deceit was used in the collection of data from the respondents.

Results and Discussion

This section centers on presenting, analyzing, and interpreting the data gathered for this study.

Quarter in Mathematics 9 that Exhibited the Lowest Mastery According to the Results of the Learning Outcomes Assessment of School Year 2022-2023

Table 2 shows the Learning Outcomes Assessment of School Year 2022-2023, which can be developed into slide-based instructional material for Mathematics 9.

Table 2. *Learning Outcomes Assessment of School Year 2022-2023*

<i>Subject</i>	<i>Percentage per Quarter</i>			
	<i>Quarter 1</i>	<i>Quarter 2</i>	<i>Quarter 3</i>	<i>Quarter 4</i>
Mathematics 9	44.28	37.92	45.26	44.30

Based on Table 2, the second quarter had the lowest percentage of learning outcomes for the School Year 2022-2023. As reflected in this quarter the 37.92 is often seen as more challenging than others since it builds on the foundational knowledge established in the first quarter, introducing more complex concepts and deeper analytical tasks. These developments require students to enhance their problem-solving skills and conceptual understanding through a step-by-step process.

Through this, the prioritized learning competencies based on the Regional Memorandum No. 383, s. 2021 and Division Memorandum No. 396, s. 2021 are as follows: (1) Illustrates situations that involve the following variations: (a) direct; (b) inverse; (c) joint; (d) combined; (2) Translates into variation statement a relationship between two quantities given by: (a) a table of values; (b) a mathematical equation; (c) a graph, and vice versa; (3) Solves problems involving variation; (4) Applies the laws involving positive integral exponents to zero and negative integral exponents; (5) Simplifies expressions with rational exponents; (6) Writes expressions with rational exponents as radicals and vice versa; (7) Derives the laws of radicals from the laws of rational exponents; (8) Simplifies radical expressions using the laws of radicals; (9) Performs operations on radical expressions; (10) Solves equations involving radical expressions; and (11) Solves problems involving radicals.

Evaluations of Mathematics Teachers and Expert Respondents on the Developed Slide-based Instructional Material in Mathematics 9

The developed slide-based instructional material in Mathematics 9 for the Second Quarter was evaluated by ten (10) Mathematics teachers and ten (10) experts from District II of the City Schools Division of Antipolo. The evaluations of the two groups of respondents

for the developed slide-based instructional material's content quality, instructional quality, technical quality, and accuracy and up-to-datedness are detailed in Tables 3 to 6 and summarized in Table 7.

Content Quality. Table 3 highlights the respondents' evaluations of the content quality of the developed slide-based instructional material.

According to Table 3, the content of the developed slide-based instructional material received a Very Satisfactory (VS) rating from teachers and expert respondents. The overall weighted mean is 3.85 in both teachers and expert respondents, along with standard deviations of 0.29 and 0.31, respectively.

Table 3. Respondents' Evaluations on Developed Slide-based Instructional Material in Terms of Content Quality
The Content of the Developed Slide-based Instructional Material is...

	Respondents			
	Teachers		Experts	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. consistent/aligned with the topics outlined in the DepEd Learning Competencies for the intended subject and grade/year level.	4.00	VS	4.00	VS
2. contributory to the enrichment, reinforcement, or mastery of the identified learning objectives.	4.00	VS	4.00	VS
3. accurate with the curriculum standards.	3.80	VS	3.80	VS
4. current and relevant to the subject matter.	3.80	VS	3.70	VS
5. logically developed and organized.	3.90	VS	3.90	VS
6. free from cultural, gender, racial, or ethnic bias.	3.70	VS	3.70	VS
7. stimulating and promoting critical thinking.	3.90	VS	3.90	VS
8. relevant to real-life situations.	3.60	VS	3.90	VS
9. appropriate to the target user level.	4.00	VS	3.90	VS
10. promoting positive values that support formative growth.	3.80	VS	3.70	VS
Overall Weighted Mean	3.85	VS	3.85	VS
Standard Deviation	0.29		0.31	

Legend: WM – Weighted Mean; SD – Standard Deviation; VI – Verbal Interpretation; VS – Very Satisfactory

Indicators 1 and 2 received a favorable rating from the respondents, signifying the consistent alignment of the content with the DepEd Learning Competencies for the corresponding grade and subject. The material also contributed to the learning objectives' enrichment, reinforcement, or mastery. This is similar to the study of Garcia (2022), which indicates that the content of the developed material is evident in the evaluation of teachers and expert respondents. Garcia emphasized that the objectives must be simple and attainable.

Instructional Quality. Table 4 highlights the respondents' evaluations of the instructional quality of the developed slide-based instructional material.

Table 4. Respondents' Evaluations on Developed Slide-based Instructional Material in Terms of Instructional Quality
The Instructional Quality of the Developed Slide-based Instructional Material is...

	Respondents			
	Teachers		Experts	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. evident, as its purpose or objective is clear and well-defined.	3.70	VS	3.80	VS
2. evident in how the material achieves its defined purpose.	4.00	VS	3.90	VS
3. inclusive of learning objectives that are clearly stated and measurable.	3.70	VS	3.90	VS
4. appropriate for the learners.	4.00	VS	3.90	VS
5. sustained with graphics, colors, and sounds for appropriate instructional reasons.	3.70	VS	3.70	VS
6. enjoyable, stimulating, challenging, and engaging.	4.00	VS	3.70	VS
7. effectively stimulating the creativity of the student.	3.80	VS	3.80	VS
8. maintained through effective feedback and learners' responses.	3.80	VS	3.80	VS
9. guaranteed that the teacher or learner controls the sequence of the presentation.	3.80	VS	4.00	VS
10. assured with integrated instruction and learners' previous experience.	3.60	VS	3.50	VS
Overall Weighted Mean	3.81	VS	3.80	VS
Standard Deviation	0.34		0.37	

Table 4 shows that the overall weighted mean ratings of 3.81 and 3.80 with standard deviations of 0.34 and 0.37, respectively, indicate that teachers and expert respondents confirmed that the developed slide-based instructional material has a Very Satisfactory (VS) rating in terms of its instructional quality. This suggests that there is only a slight difference of 0.01 between the weighted mean, which means that teachers and expert respondents almost have the same evaluation of the developed slide-based instructional material in terms of instructional quality.

The ratings show that indicators 2 and 4 received a favorable response from teachers and expert respondents. This implied that the instructional quality of the developed slide-based instructional material is evident in how the material achieves its defined purpose and appropriateness for the learners.

Similar results were achieved by Buitre (2023), where the evaluations of two groups of respondents agreed that the instructional quality

of Electronic Strategic Material (E-SIM) in Grade 7 Biology was acceptable to both science teachers and experts. Buitre also mentioned that the materials provide clear instructions, are user-friendly, and can be independently used by the target user, which is why science teachers and expert respondents strongly accept the Electronic Strategic Material.

Technical Quality. Table 5 displays the respondent's evaluation of the technical quality of the developed slide-based instructional material.

Based on Table 5, teachers and the expert respondents found that the technical quality of the developed slide-based instructional material has a Very Satisfactory (VS) rating. The overall weighted mean ratings for teachers and experts are 3.87 and 3.84, with standard deviations of 0.36 and 0.35, respectively. This suggests that there is only a minimal difference of 0.03 in the weighted mean ratings between teachers and experts.

Table 5. Respondents' Evaluations on Developed Slide-based Instructional Material in Terms of Technical Quality

The Technical Quality of the Developed Slide-based Instructional Material is...	Respondents			
	Teachers		Experts	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. showing screen displays (text) that are uncluttered, easy to read, and aesthetically pleasing.	3.90	VS	3.90	VS
2. projecting visual presentations (non-text) that are clear, not pixelated, or distorted.	3.80	VS	3.70	VS
3. presenting visuals that sustain interest and do not distract learners' attention.	3.90	VS	3.80	VS
4. providing users with accurate visual representation of the concept discussed.	3.90	VS	3.90	VS
5. effectively supporting materials that are designed to complement and enhance the learning experience.	3.90	VS	3.70	VS
6. allowing the target user to navigate freely through the material.	3.70	VS	3.90	VS
7. engaging and interactive.	3.90	VS	3.80	VS
8. easily and independently used.	3.90	VS	3.80	VS
9. free from technical problems (Slide animations and Slide transitions).	3.90	VS	3.90	VS
10. sequential and ensures a smooth flow of ideas.	3.90	VS	4.00	VS
Overall Weighted Mean	3.87	VS	3.84	VS
Standard Deviation	0.36		0.35	

Based on the ratings, Indicator 10 favorable response from teachers and expert respondents. This suggests that the material was organized sequentially, allowing for a smooth flow of ideas. The results align with the study conducted by Corpuz (2023), where she highlighted that the material is deemed acceptable in terms of integration of technology, engagement, and student interaction.

Accuracy and Up-to-Datedness. Table 6 depicts the respondents' evaluations of the accuracy and up-to-datedness of the developed slide-based instructional material.

The data on the table 6 shows that the overall weighted mean ratings of 3.88 and 3.77 with standard deviations of 0.33 and 0.43, respectively, indicate that teachers and expert respondents confirmed that the developed slide-based instructional material has a Very Satisfactory (VS) rating in terms of its accuracy and up-to-datedness.

Table 6. Respondents' Evaluations on Developed Slide-based Instructional Material in Terms of Accuracy and Up-to-Datedness

The Accuracy and Up-to-datedness of the Developed Slide-based Instructional Material is...	Respondents			
	Teachers		Experts	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
free from Conceptual error.	3.90	VS	3.70	VS
free from Factual errors.	3.90	VS	3.90	VS
free from Grammatical and/or typographical errors.	3.90	VS	3.70	VS
free from Computational errors.	3.80	VS	3.90	VS
not containing obsolete information.	3.90	VS	3.70	VS
utilizing visuals and/or graphics that are timely and relevant.	3.90	VS	3.70	VS
Overall Weighted Mean	3.88	VS	3.77	VS
Standard Deviation	0.33		0.43	

Based on the evaluations provided by teachers and expert respondents. It has been established that Indicator 2 received the most favorable rating. This indicates that educational material was remarkably accurate and free from factual errors. The results align with the studies conducted by Buitre (2023) implying that the perceptions of teachers and expert respondents in her study on Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials indicate that they are firmly accepted –based on Accuracy and Up-to-datedness. As per the science teachers' and expert respondents' points of view, the material is very satisfactory and adheres to the standards concerning details, which mainly focus on the information's accuracy, correctness, and timeliness.

Summary. Table 7 provides the respondents' summary on evaluating the content quality, instructional quality, technical quality, and accuracy and up-to-dateness on the developed slide-based instructional material.

According to the data presented in Table 7, the slide-based instructional material that was developed received Very Satisfactory (VS) ratings from both teachers and expert respondents. The evaluations encompassed content quality, instructional quality, technical quality, and accuracy and up-to-dateness. The respective grand weighted mean ratings are 3.85 and 3.82.

Table 7. *Summary of Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Instructional Material*

Criteria	Respondents			
	Teachers		Experts	
	OWM	VI	OWM	VI
Content Quality	3.85	VS	3.85	VS
Instructional Quality	3.81	VS	3.80	VS
Technical Quality	3.87	VS	3.84	VS
Accuracy and up-to-dateness	3.88	VS	3.77	VS
Grand Weighted Mean	3.85	VS	3.82	VS

Legend: OWM – Overall Weighted Mean

According to the data presented in Table 7, the slide-based instructional material that was developed received Very Satisfactory (VS) ratings from both teachers and expert respondents. The evaluations encompassed content quality, instructional quality, technical quality, and accuracy and up-to-dateness. The respective grand weighted mean ratings are 3.85 and 3.82.

This clearly shows that teachers and expert respondents evaluated the instructional material as Very Satisfactory (VS) and met the criteria of four factors.

Test of Significant Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Slide-based Instructional Material in Mathematics 9

The computed difference in the evaluation of teachers and expert respondents on the development of slide-based instructional material is presented in Tables 8 to 11, with a summary provided in Table 12.

As depicted in Table 8, the computed t value of 0.00 falls below the critical t value of 2.10 with 18 degrees of freedom. At a significance level of 5%, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. Consequently, this suggests that there is no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed slide-based instructional material in Mathematics 9 regarding Content Quality.

Table 8. *Test of Significant Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Slide-based Instructional Material in Mathematics 9 as to Content Quality*

Respondents	n	OWM	SD	Computed t Value	Critical t value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	10	3.85	0.29	0.00	2.10	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
Experts	10	3.85	0.31				

Note: n – Sample Size; SD – Standard Deviation; H0 – Null Hypothesis; Level of Significance, $\alpha = 5\%$; Degrees of Freedom, $df = 18$

This suggests that the Content Quality of the developed slide-based instructional material is aligned with the DepEd Learning Competencies relevant to the corresponding grade and subject. Furthermore, the material also contributed to the enrichment, reinforcement, or mastery of the learning objectives.

As reflected in Table 9, the computed t value of 0.06 is lower than the critical t value of 2.10. At a significance level of 5%, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, this supports that there is no significant difference between the evaluations of two groups of respondents on the developed slide-based instructional material in Mathematics 9 regarding instructional quality.

Table 9. *Test of Significant Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Slide-based Instructional Material in Mathematics 9 as to Instructional Quality*

Respondents	n	OWM	SD	Computed t Value	Critical t value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	10	3.81	0.34	0.06	2.10	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
Experts	10	3.80	0.37				

This suggests that the Instructional Quality of the developed slide-based instructional material is evident in how the material achieves its defined purpose and appropriateness for the learners.

Table 10. *Test of Significant Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Slide-based Instructional Material in Mathematics 9 as to Technical Quality*

Respondents	n	OWM	SD	Computed t Value	Critical t value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	10	3.87	0.36	0.19	2.10	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
Experts	10	3.84	0.35				

Table 10 indicates that the computed t value of 0.19 falls below the critical t value of 2.10. So, the statistical decision is to fail to reject the null hypothesis. At a significance level of 5%, this supports that there is no significant difference in the evaluations of two groups

of respondents on the developed slide-based instructional material in Mathematics 9 concerning technical quality.

This indicates that the respondents share a common perspective that the developed slide-based instructional material features uncluttered screen displays, is easy to read, is visually appealing, and accurately represents the discussed concepts.

Table 11 examines the significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed slide-based instructional material in Mathematics 9 as to accuracy and up-to-datedness.

Table 11. *Test of Significant Difference Between the Evaluations of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Slide-based Instructional Material in Mathematics 9 as to accuracy and up-to-datedness*

Respondents	n	OWM	SD	Computed t Value	Critical t value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	10	3.88	0.33	0.64	2.10	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
Experts	10	3.77	0.43				

As depicted in Table 11, the computed t value of 0.64 is lower than the critical t value of 2.10. Consequently, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. At a significance level of 5%, this indicates no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents concerning the developed slide-based instructional material regarding accuracy and up-to-datedness.

This means the two groups of respondents have the same views that the developed slide-based instructional material is free from factual errors, ensuring that students receive accurate and reliable information.

Table 12 summarizes the test of significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed slide-based instructional material in Mathematics 9.

Table 12. *Summary of the Test of Significant Difference Between the Evaluations of the two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Slide-based Instructional Material in Mathematics 9*

Criteria	Teachers		Experts		tcomputed Value	Decision	Interpretation
	OWM	SD	OWM	SD			
Content Quality	3.85	0.29	3.85	0.31	0.00	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
Instructional Quality	3.81	0.34	3.80	0.37	0.06	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
Technical Quality	3.87	0.36	3.84	0.35	0.19	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant
Accuracy and Up-to-Datedness	3.88	0.33	3.77	0.43	0.64	Fail to Reject the H0	Not Significant

Note: $\alpha = 5\%$ Critical t Value = 2.10

As portrayed in Table 12, the evaluations of mathematics teachers and expert respondents regarding the developed slide-based instructional material in Mathematics 9 concerning content quality, instructional quality, technical quality, and accuracy and up-to-datedness, exhibit no significant differences. This is evidenced by the computed t values, which are lower than the critical t value. Thus, the evaluations of the respondents are the same.

This indicates that the evaluations of two groups of respondents on the instructional material are “Very Satisfactory” and have met the standards with respect to the four criteria.

This result suggests that the developed slide-based instructional material has the potential to enhance the academic performance of Grade 9 students. Incorporating educational technology into the teaching-learning process can significantly enhance learners' interest. Engaging with interactive materials not only enhances their interest but also guarantees their readiness to succeed in a digitalized world.

Comments and Suggestions of the Respondents for Further Improvement of the Slide-based Instructional Material in Mathematics 9

Here are some comments and recommendations from mathematics teachers and expert respondents on the developed slide-based instructional material in Mathematics 9.

Comments. The following are the comments given by the respondents on the developed slide-based instructional material in Mathematics 9.

The slides are comprehensively presented, with examples and activities that are easy to understand and meet key learning skills.

This teaching material is very effective for Mathematics 9 and provides interesting interactive features to help learners actively participate in discussions.

The quality of the materials is very impressive.

Your detailed and comprehensive content will help improve learning outcomes and demonstrate your commitment to improving education.

The use of slide-based teaching materials can be beneficial in mathematics courses because it allows visualization of mathematical concepts and processes.

Mathematics teachers and expert respondents praised the material for its capacity to improve mathematics learning outcomes, citing its comprehensive content, effectiveness in promoting active engagement, impressive quality, and the benefits of visualizing mathematical concepts.

Suggestions. The following are the suggestions given by the respondents on the developed slide-based instructional material in Mathematics 9.

If necessary, please consider including video links or video clips (tutorials) as supplemental resources to the appropriate MELC.

Use different slide presentation templates.

Lessen the transparency of the visibility of the logos/picture in the background of slides.

Consider incorporating additional real-life examples in the lesson. This will enhance learners' understanding and relevance and promote retention.

Mathematics teachers and expert respondents suggest that the instructional material could be improved by incorporating video tutorials as supplementary resources. Mecida S. et al. (2023) supported this notion, indicating that the use of short video lessons can improve academic performance in mathematics by enhancing students' comprehension, particularly through step-by-step process instructions and solutions. Additionally, respondents recommended utilizing varied slide templates, reducing background transparency and including more real-life examples to enhance understanding and relevance for learners while promoting retention.

Conclusions

Based on the findings obtained, this conclusion is made:

As evidenced by evaluations of two groups of respondents, the instructional material is acceptable to the learners and has the potential to significantly enhance the mathematical literacy of grade 9 learners, having received positive feedback from Mathematics teachers and expert respondents.

Based on the conclusions drawn in this research, these recommendations are suggested:

The developed slide-based instructional material for Grade 9 students of Maximo L. Gatlabayan Memorial National High School may be used by Grade 9 students upon successful evaluations of mathematics teachers and experts regarding content quality, instructional quality, technical quality, and accuracy and up-to-datedness.

Educational institutions may prioritize offering seminars and training to incorporate educational technology into teaching and learning.

Other teachers across different levels and learning areas are encouraged to develop other instructional material to make the teaching-learning process more effective and productive.

Future researchers aiming to achieve a normal distribution of data carefully select an appropriate number of respondents.

Other researchers may conduct similar research in mathematics or other learning areas related to developing instructional material.

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